

Results in Physics

Supplementary Material for
**Inverse Design of Octagonal Plasmonic
Structure for Switching Using Deep Learning**

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This PDF file includes:

Notes S1 to S7

Figures S1 to S9

References (1 to 13)

Supplement Note 1. Design and Simulation of AOPS

Note 1.1: Electromagnetic theory of AOPS design and modeling

This research builds upon successful prior endeavors to formulate and operate All-optical plasmonic switches (AOPSs). The design integrates materials and arrangements widely recognized for superior performance in switching applications. Recent advancements in manufacturing technologies have enabled this design [1, 2], which includes a circular resonator connected to input and output waveguides of varying widths. Figure 2 (in the main manuscript) illustrates that the AOPS structures feature a silver film coated with a low refractive index material, specifically an Au/SiO₂ composite. This composite employs an Au/SiO₂ blend with a refractive index (n_0) of 1.47 and a Kerr nonlinear coefficient (n_2) of 2.07×10^{-9} cm²/W [3]. This selection facilitates the generation of surface plasmon resonance phenomena that significantly bolster third-order optical nonlinear susceptibility. The AOPS's cladding layer is air, with a foundational layer made of glass. For practical fabrication facilitation, the silver and Au/SiO₂ layers are 50 nm thick, accompanied by a 100 nm thick glass film serving as the substrate. The resonant wavelengths (λ_r) are calculated using the equation [4]:

$$\lambda_r = Ln_{\text{eff}}/m \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where L denotes the effective length, n_{eff} represents the effective refractive index, and m is an integer. The Kerr effect is responsible for the nonlinearity observed in Ring Resonators (RRs), wherein the refractive index changes due to the Kerr nonlinear coefficient and the intensity of the incident light. For a more detailed explanation, please refer to the provided reference [5].

$$n = n_0 + n_2 I \quad (\text{S2})$$

In this equation, n_0 represents the linear refractive index, n_2 represents the nonlinear refractive index coefficient, and I represents light intensity. Surface Plasmon Polaritons (SPPs), mainly excited through Transverse Magnetic (TM) polarization in metallic structures [6], exhibit exceptional electromagnetic field intensification, confinement beyond the wavelength scale, and heightened sensitivity to adjacent dielectric environments. These properties make SPPs particularly useful for biosensing [7, 8], nanophotonics [9, 10], and metamaterials [11] applications. The engagement with TM-polarized light at resonant wavelengths triggers the excitation of SPPs within the RR structure. Silver is chosen for its advantageous complex dielectric constant delineated by the Drude model [1, 12].

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_\infty - \omega_p^2 / (\omega^2 - j\gamma_p \omega) \quad (\text{S3})$$

In this context, ε_∞ is equivalent to 1.95, the relative permittivity occurring at infinite frequency. The angular frequency of the incident light wave is represented by ω . Also, γ_p , defined as the electron collision frequency, is quantified as 2×10^{13} rad/s while the plasma frequency, ω_p , is quantified as 1.37×10^{16} rad/s.

It is common practice to break down the dielectric constant into real and imaginary components. The Drude-Lorentz model is widely utilized in various domains, particularly for characterizing electronic transitions in metals and explaining SPP resonance phenomena. This model is an effective tool for identifying electronic transitions in metals, accurately illustrating the actions of free electrons and their impact on surface plasmon resonance. It is particularly effective for materials with more free electrons than bound electrons. Drude's free-electron model is used to compute the dielectric constant, facilitating the separation of its real and imaginary components. The dielectric constant can be defined as:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{real}} = 1 - \frac{\omega_p^2 \tau^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{imag}} = \frac{\omega_p^2 \tau}{\omega(\omega + \omega^2 \tau^2)} \quad (\text{S5})$$

To simplify Eq. (S1) and Eq. (S2) for metals in the near-infrared frequency range, we will adopt the methodology suggested by Johnson and Christy. This simplification is based on the fact that the angular frequency (ω) is significantly greater than the inverse of the relaxation time ($1/\tau$). Consequently, the dielectric constant can be expressed in a simplified form.

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = 1 + \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^2} + j \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega^3 \tau} = \varepsilon_{\text{real}} + \varepsilon_{\text{imag}} \quad (\text{S6})$$

The terms $\varepsilon_{\text{real}}$ and $\varepsilon_{\text{imag}}$ define the complex relative permittivity ($\varepsilon(\omega)$) in a given situation. The real and imaginary parts of the complex refractive index (n) are denoted as n and κ , respectively. These two quantities are interrelated as follows [13]:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{real}} = n^2 - \kappa^2 \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$\varepsilon_{\text{imag}} = 2n\kappa \quad (\text{S8})$$

To explore the intrinsic physical characteristics of plasmonics, we utilized the FDTD method, a computational approach for solving classical Maxwell's equations. This method incorporates the sinusoidal time dependence of the electric field as $E(r, t) = E(r)e^{-j\omega t}$ and allows us to derive the Helmholtz equation from the fundamental equations of Maxwell. The resulting mathematical expression can be represented as the Johnson and Christy technique, enabling us to determine the real and imaginary parts of the complex refractive index and calculate the coefficients of reflection and transmission.

$$\nabla^2 E + k_0^2 \varepsilon E = 0 \quad (\text{S9})$$

The symbol k_0 represents the wavevector, while the formula $E(x, y, z) = E(x, y)e^{j\beta z}$ describes the propagating field, and β represents the propagation constant. The complex form of the propagation constant is expressed as $\gamma = \alpha + j\beta$, with α representing the attenuation constant. When α equals zero, the term $\gamma = j\beta$ exclusively signifies the propagation along the z-axis.

Note 1.2: FDTD simulation of AOPS

In this study, we utilized the FDTD numerical method to investigate the proposed configurations' linear and nonlinear optical properties. The method accurately models the system's visual response, and we ensured enhanced spatial resolution by carefully selecting mesh dimensions of $\Delta x = \Delta z = 0.5$ nm. We implemented a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) as an absorptive boundary condition to minimize reflections at the simulation domain's boundaries. The PML has proven highly effective in absorbing outgoing waves and significantly reducing reflections, thereby improving the accuracy of our results. Our AOPS architecture features a silver film coupled with an Au/SiO₂ layer with a low refractive index, offering control over SPPs and enabling the desired switching functionality. Air was chosen as the cladding layer and glass as the base due to their favorable optical properties, making them standard materials for plasmonic device fabrication. We determined a 50 nm thickness for both the silver film and Au/SiO₂ layer to optimize device efficiency, taking into account the impact of manufacturing processes on device performance.

By integrating a 100 nm glass substrate, we have improved the mechanical support and stability of the device. Our team utilized the FDTD method to conduct a meticulous exploration of the linear and nonlinear dynamics of the intricate AOPS configuration, resulting in a comprehensive analysis of its optical behavior. This thorough analysis provided valuable insights into the system's distinctive features and behavior under varying conditions.

Supplement Note 2. DNN formulation

Now that we clearly understand the AOPS construction presented in Fig. 2 (in the main manuscript), we can delve into the mathematical framework behind the forward and inverse models. These models play a vital role in formulating the problem for the Neural Network, as they connect the input variables to the transmission spectra. By utilizing the geometric design parameters C_i associated with the AOPS, we can create a forward model that enables us to calculate the transmission spectrum for both output ports. We can use the morphism function $\mathbf{M}$ and the relevant input variables to obtain the transmission spectra T_1 and T_2 , which correspond to output ports 1 and 2.

$$T_j^\lambda = \mathbf{M}(C_1 = W_{\text{bus}}, C_2 = W_{\text{drop}}, C_3 = W_{\text{octagon}}, C_4 = G_{\text{bus}}, C_5 = G_{\text{drop}}, C_6 = \lambda) \quad (\text{S10})$$

In this formula, there are several variables to consider. The first variable, W_{bus} , stands for the width of waveguide 1. The second variable, W_{drop} , refers to the width of waveguide 2. The third variable, W_{octagon} , indicates the width of the octagonal waveguide. G_{bus} represents the gap of waveguide 1, while G_{drop} shows the gap of waveguide 2. Lastly, λ represents the wavelength of the input light, which can range from 1000 nm to 1800 nm. By incorporating the input light's wavelength into the neural network's forward model, we have enhanced its ability to forecast transmittance values across various wavelengths, whether single or wide wavelengths. In this mathematical framework, we have added the input light's wavelength as an input variable in the NN's forward model, allowing it to calculate transmittance values for both single and multiple wavelengths. To establish the optimal estimator for the forward model, we define an objective function as follows:

$$\min_{i=1,2,\dots,6} \{ \|\hat{\mathbf{M}}(C_i) - g\| \} \quad (\text{S11})$$

In the equation discussed above, the predicted function is represented by the symbol $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ and is compared to the ground truth, g , which refers to the actual observed values. The primary challenge in DL lies in identifying the most optimal estimator for $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ based on the available training data. On the other hand, an inverse problem involves reconstructing the design space using the available transmission values. Our approach is innovative and differs from traditional methods. We utilize Eq. (S10) to derive a design space from the transmission spectra, where T_j represents the transmission spectra. This design space can be achieved using the following inverse function.

$$C_i = \mathbf{M}^{-1}(T_j) \quad (\text{S12})$$

Our research methodology is distinct, as we acknowledge a prevalent obstacle in our industry. Conventional analytical techniques frequently fail to determine the inverse function for AOPS configurations. To overcome this challenge, we offer a fresh outlook by advocating using DL strategies as a substitute solution. DL is a potent resource for nonlinear approximation, and our study pioneers an enhanced approach for both forward and inverse models. This groundbreaking methodology fosters a holistic comprehension of the intricate behavior of AOPS, representing a substantial stride forward in the field.

Supplement Note 3. Dataset discussion

This section offers a concise overview of the training dataset used to train the Deep Neural Network (DNN). The training dataset is an essential component that aids in identifying hidden patterns and generating accurate predictions. With access to a complete and precise training dataset, the DNN showcases its ability to handle varying inputs and assign appropriate weightage via the activation function of each neuron. In Fig. S1a, we can view the input training dataset implemented to train the established NN. The dataset used in this study comprises 14,745,600 data points computed via the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) method.

Within the dataset, various parameters are depicted by differently colored bars in Fig. S1a. These parameters include C_1 , the width of the bus waveguide; C_2 , the width of the drop waveguide; C_3 , the width of the octagon waveguide; C_4 , the gap in the bus waveguide; and C_5 , the gap in the drop waveguide. Utilizing the output dataset displayed in Fig. S1b, the constructed DNN is trained and capable of predicting outcomes.

The dataset showcases spectral information obtained through FDTD methodology, revealing transmission spectra for both the through and drop ports. In Fig. S1b, the blue bars correspond to the through port's transmission spectra, while the orange bars illustrate that of the drop port. This dataset is a reference point for training and assessing the DNN's efficiency. As seen in Fig. S1, the presentation is fair and uniform in its distribution of information.

When a histogram displays a uniform distribution of data points across its various bars, input and output datasets are evenly distributed, with no noticeable bias or irregularities. By prioritizing fair distribution and inclusivity of datasets, we can significantly improve our NN model's ability to generalize and draw accurate conclusions. The distribution presents an exciting opportunity to develop further and enhance the model's overall capabilities.

Fig. S1. Histograms of the data distribution. Histograms visually represent the distribution of input and output variables. (a) The input data set used for NN training consists of several configurational parameters of the resonator structure, including C_1 , the width of the bus waveguide; C_2 , the width of the drop waveguide; C_3 , the width of the octagon waveguide; C_4 , the gap of the bus waveguide; and C_5 , the gap of the drop waveguide. A histogram displays the dispersion and occurrence rates of these input factors. (b) Similarly, the output data set used in the NN training reflects the transmission spectra of the resonator's output ports 1 and 2. A histogram provides a clear and concise summary of the transmission spectra's distribution and notable characteristics for each port.

Supplement Note 4. Analysis of the computational cost

Note 4.1: Comparison of the computational cost of NNs with various architectures

The upcoming analysis will center on evaluating the effectiveness of the NN and its computational expenses. Generating extensive training datasets for DNNs necessitates substantial computing resources, leading to obstacles in automatically producing data points, particularly in underrepresented domains not yet incorporated in the datasets. These challenges are further intensified when considering the constraints of computational resources and the extent of engagement researchers require in data curation, making the situation more complex.

Exploring techniques that can improve datasets while maintaining model generalization is crucial. Figure S2 sheds light on the variations in training execution times, contingent on the number of neurons and hidden layers. This analysis estimates the computational expenses of processing a single transmission spectrum during DNN training by modifying the number of neurons across diverse hidden layer configurations. The results reveal that boosting the complexity of DNN architectures and the number of neurons necessitates more excellent computational resources.

It is worth mentioning that when a DNN has reached a certain point with eleven layers and 160 neurons in the central layer, adding more layers and neurons may not further reduce the

loss function. This can pose a challenge known as the vanishing gradient problem, requiring the DNN to undergo additional computation and time to improve its predictions during training. Nonetheless, the DNN demonstrates impressive performance, outpacing traditional FDTD solvers that typically take thousands of seconds to compute plasmonic RR optical responses using automated meshes. While creating an extensive dataset through computationally intensive electromagnetic simulations is crucial, it only needs to be done once. Moreover, [Note 5](#) elaborates on how the Taguchi method substantially reduces the data necessary for network training.

Upon completion of its training, the DNN can swiftly predict new configurations, indicating its potential to accelerate computational tasks post-training. These findings underscore the nuanced interplay between computational cost and predictive accuracy within the DNN architecture. When selecting the optimal configuration for a given task, it is vital to thoughtfully weigh the available computational resources against the desired level of precision. Pursuing an optimal balance between computational expenditure and prediction accuracy is a crucial area for further study, revealing the intricate relationship between efficiency and efficacy in the evolution of DNNs.

Fig. S2. An examination of the computational costs. An examination of the computational expenses of various neural network architectures across three different epochs (a) 1500, (b) 2000, and (c) 2500. The number of neurons was adjusted according to the hidden layer setup. A complex DNN with a higher neuron count typically requires more computing resources. However, a configuration comprising six layers and sixty neurons demonstrated no noteworthy enhancement in loss metrics with additional layers or neurons. It was observed that adding more layers and neurons could result in the vanishing gradient issue, as depicted in [Fig. S7](#) and [Fig. S8](#), while also increasing computational costs.

Note 4.2: Comparison of the computational cost between DL and numerical method.

Our objective is to thoroughly investigate the costs involved in implementing DL techniques versus Finite Element Method (FEM) and FDTD methods. Within [Fig. S3](#), we have displayed the computational expenses associated with FEM and FDTD methods across a range of meshing strategies. Through this analysis, we aim to assess the computational load of DL as compared to FEM and FDTD techniques. To be specific, [Fig. S3](#) depicts the CPU time required to execute FEM and FDTD methodologies under various mesh configurations. It was observed that utilizing the most refined mesh size resulted in computational durations of 5871 seconds for FEM and 4515 seconds for FDTD, respectively.

Our study reveals that the FDTD and FEM methods exhibit progressively increasing computational times across various mesh levels. In contrast, the DL methodology is exceptionally efficient, with a computational time of just a fraction of a second. This remarkable reduction in processing time translates to significant gains in efficiency and productivity for practitioners.

Our research introduces an innovative strategy that utilizes a DNN to approximate spectral data, significantly reducing the processing time associated with the DL technique. Combining these individual components' temporal metrics allows the cumulative time required for task completion to be accurately determined. This approach identifies optimal techniques and

models for various complex photonic devices, enabling the determination of execution times for batches or extended epochs.

Fig. S3. A comparative analysis of the computational costs. A thorough examination was conducted to evaluate the computational expenses linked with using the FEM and FDTD methods. Upon employing the most refined mesh settings, the simulations took 7750 seconds for FEM and 5962 seconds for FDTD. However, the use of DL techniques resulted in a decrease in computational time to less than a second. This notable reduction in simulation time is a significant benefit, resulting in considerable time savings. It emphasizes the efficacy of DL techniques in simplifying the computational process, offering a feasible alternative to traditional numerical simulation approaches.

This comparative analysis highlights the exceptional computational efficiency of the DL method, particularly when compared to the FEM and FDTD methodologies across a range of mesh densities. The significant reduction in processing time brought about by the DL approach paves the way for enhanced and faster analysis of photonic devices, leading to increased productivity and innovation in the field.

Supplement Note 5. Taguchi method

The study's experimental design incorporated the Taguchi method, renowned for its statistical prowess in assessing the influence of different process parameters and accurately delineating the correlation between input and output variables. In contrast to conventional methods, such as the Factorial design, this approach is more effective as it obviates the requirement for numerous experiments, thus economizing time and effectively identifying optimal conditions.

Three distinct criteria were used to evaluate the property of interest: "lower is better," "higher is better," and "nominal is better." The study's objectives were considered when selecting the contrast and Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) criteria. Specifically, the "higher is better" criterion was used for contrast, while the "lower is better" criterion was used for FWHM to achieve high contrast between the ports and a low FWHM. The average values of each parameter were used to measure their influence on the contrast ratio and FWHM. An Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was then conducted to determine the significance and contribution of each parameter to the output characteristics, precisely the contrast between the ports and the FWHM. The best experimental conditions were predicted based on the insights gained from the average values and ANOVA results.

In this investigation, the impact of five parameters was studied, each having three different levels. These parameters were the widths of the bus, drop, and octagon waveguides (35, 45, and 55 nm) and the gaps within the bus and drop waveguides (15, 20, and 25 nm). The Taguchi method was implemented, which reduced the workload to just 18 runs as opposed to the 243 experiments required by a factorial design. [Table S1](#) provides a detailed explanation of the

method's efficiency and effectiveness in experimental design. The study was conducted carefully, measuring the contrast ratio between the ports and the FWHM across eighteen simulations under the conditions described in Table S1.

The system's resonance characteristics were measured to examine how configurational parameters affect them. The main effects plots in Fig. S4 show how the average contrast ratio and FWHM values change concerning the configurational parameters. These plots offer valuable insights into identifying the optimal processing conditions. The results indicate that the width of the bus (W_{bus}), drop (W_{drop}), and octagon (W_{octagon}) waveguides, as well as the gaps within the bus (G_{bus}) and drop (G_{drop}) waveguides, significantly impact the contrast ratio and FWHM. As shown in Fig. S5, the pie chart further distills that the average significance attributed to these parameters is about 9%, 14%, 5%, 28%, and 45%. The results of the ANOVA offer insights into the significance of each configuration factor (Table S2).

The investigation successfully met its primary objective in its final stages by utilizing the Taguchi robust design methodology to minimize variability surrounding the product's performance metrics. Through this approach, significant parameters were identified and optimized to enhance the product's quality attributes by minimizing the impact of insignificant factors. By applying Taguchi's robust design principles, the experimental procedures were significantly streamlined, reducing both time and expenses while improving the product's quality attributes. In the context of resonance characteristics, a strategic approach was taken to select an appropriate orthogonal array for the study, resulting in only 18 necessary experiments. The outcomes were optimal, rendering 225 additional experiments unnecessary and ultimately saving time and costs while improving output quality.

Table S1. Simulation values of the resonance characteristics of the AOPS for Taguchi experiments.

Config. No.	Configurational parameters (nm)					resonance characteristics	
	W_{bus} (C_1)	W_{drop} (C_2)	W_{octagon} (C_3)	G_{bus} (C_4)	G_{drop} (C_5)	T_2-T_1 (%)	FWHM (nm)
1	35	35	35	15	15	0.25	63
2	35	45	45	20	20	0.23	27
3	35	55	55	25	25	0	18
4	45	35	35	20	20	0.33	42
5	45	45	45	25	25	0.14	24
6	45	55	55	15	15	0.49	52
7	55	35	45	15	25	0.39	37
8	55	45	55	20	15	0.14	45
9	55	55	35	25	20	0.04	25
10	35	35	55	25	20	-0.08	26
11	35	45	35	15	25	0.31	36
12	35	55	45	20	15	0.21	33
13	45	35	45	25	15	-0.14	50
14	45	45	55	15	20	0.46	44
15	45	55	35	20	25	0.24	31
16	55	35	55	20	25	0.22	30
17	55	45	35	25	15	-0.1	35
18	55	55	45	15	20	0.27	30

A definitive conclusion can be reached upon careful analysis of the data and the computational resources required for various configurational parameters. The gaps between the octagonal ring and waveguides significantly affect the resonance characteristics of All-Optical Plasmonic Switch (AOPS) and the efficiency of Neural Network (NN) training, thus making them essential for enhancing the system's performance. The results obtained from the Taguchi

method are presented in Fig. S6 in a visual format, along with considerations of the computational resources' costs.

Fig. S4. The main effect plots. The analyses depict the effect of five configurational parameters on (a) the contrast ratio and (b) the FWHM. By conducting a main effect analysis, we can evaluate each parameter's distinct impact on the response variable while maintaining other factors at a constant level. This enables us to comprehend the importance of each parameter in determining the quality and performance of the AOPS.

This research is significant in demonstrating the effectiveness of Taguchi's robust design in enhancing the performance characteristics of NNs and their training processes while also reducing manufacturing expenses associated with dataset generation. The results affirm Taguchi's robust design as a valuable resource in engineering and optimization, with the potential to refine training quality, minimize data generation expenses, and secure significant economic benefits in nanophotonics. This investigation contributes to the existing pool of knowledge by clarifying the role of Taguchi's robust design in engineering and optimizing data generation processes. It highlights the methodology's usefulness in identifying optimal parameter resolutions for dataset creation, leading to improved accuracy and reduced loss.

Supplement Note 6. Optimizing hyperparameters of DNN

This section focuses on enhancing the predictive accuracy of a DNN by optimizing its hyperparameters with regard to Mean Squared Error (MSE). To ensure maximum effectiveness, a consistent learning rate of 0.1 was maintained across all predictive models. Fig. S7a showcases a graph that displays the MSE outcomes for an NN that underwent 2000 training epochs and was configured with 160 neurons in the central layer. The independent variable in this graph is the number of hidden layers. The results reveal that a conventional NN with only one hidden layer falls short in proficient prediction tasks due to its lack of complexity, which is crucial for modeling the nuanced correlations within the dataset.

Table S2. The ANOVA results provide insights into the significance of each configurational factor on the resonance characteristics.

Configurational Parameter	Degrees of Freedom (f)	Sum of Squares (S)	Variance (V)	Pure Sum (S')	Percent P (%)
$W_{\text{bus}} (C_1)$	2	182.333	91.166	156.904	9.004
$W_{\text{drop}} (C_2)$	2	296.333	148.166	270.904	14.093
$W_{\text{octagon}} (C_3)$	2	80.333	40.166	54.904	4.451
$G_{\text{bus}} (C_4)$	2	604	302	578.572	27.829
$G_{\text{drop}} (C_5)$	2	987.999	493.999	962.57	44.971

Fig. S5. Pie charts depicting the significance of each configurational parameter. The pie chart represents the significance of each configurational parameter on resonance characteristics.

Fig. S6. Visualizing the significance and computational cost. Both C₄ and C₅ significantly influence the resonance characteristics of AOPS and the effectiveness of NN training. By examining these parameters, one can better understand how these factors affect the performance of generated datasets on NN training.

This study emphasizes the limitations of simpler neural architectures in tackling complex, nonlinear challenges. In contrast, deeper NNs, like the one examined in this research, demonstrate a more remarkable ability to recognize and integrate complicated features, essential for predictive tasks of high complexity. It is worth noting that increasing the number of iterations leads to decreased MSE values. Furthermore, MSE significantly decreases as the number of hidden layers rises, finally stabilizing at 13 layers. Consequently, an NN structure with 11 hidden layers was identified as the ideal hyperparameter configuration, balancing low MSE outcomes and reduced computational demands.

This study aimed to enhance the operational efficiency of DNNs by carefully selecting the most appropriate hyperparameters. Initially, the methodology involved establishing a relationship between the number of dependent hidden layers (N_i) and the neuron count (N_n) in the central layer, which was determined using the formula $N_n = 2^{(N_i-1)/2}$. The investigation was then extended using the Fibonacci sequence to examine neuron distributions across different scales.

The study documented the impact of increasing the number of epochs and augmenting neuron quantities on MSE metrics across 9, 11, and 13 hidden layers, as depicted in Fig. S7b, c, and d. To enhance DNN performance, a series of neuron configurations following the Fibonacci sequence, consisting of one, two, three, five, and eight neurons, were rigorously

tested. The corresponding MSE outcomes for these configurations were outlined through violet, yellow, orange, blue, and green trajectories, respectively.

A meticulous analysis determined that a configuration consisting of 160 neurons was the most fitting choice for the DNN. This decision was based on its exceptional performance, characterized by decreased MSE and improved convergence rates. This strategic selection was crucial in enhancing the DNN's operational efficiency and identifying the hyperparameters that produced the best outcomes.

Fig. S7. The MSE of validation across diverse configurations. An analysis of validation set loss metrics across a range of hidden layer and neuron configurations. (a) The evaluation includes exhaustive documentation of MSE metrics for various hidden layer setups while maintaining a consistent neuron count of 160 in the central layer. The assessment covers systems with hidden layers of 1, 5, 9, 11, and 13. Networks with limited layers may struggle to capture complex relationships, while those with more layers are better equipped to detect subtle features embedded within the dataset. The MSE metrics for different neuron counts in the central layer (1, 2, 3, 5, and 8) are systematically recorded when the hidden layer count is constant at (b) 9, (c) 11, and (d) 13. Observations suggest that networks with a single neuron may not be suitable for intricate tasks, while those with a higher neuron count greatly enhance a DNN's analytical ability. This improvement facilitates the network's ability to detect finer patterns and correlations within the data, highlighting the pivotal role of neuron density in the central layer in optimizing network performance. This exploration clarifies the impact of architectural choices on DNN proficiency and emphasizes the delicate balance between depth and neuron distribution as crucial determinants of model efficacy.

To ensure a comprehensive evaluation of the DNN's capabilities, we kept the epoch count constant at 2000 while the number of neurons in the central layer remained fixed at 160. This approach allowed for a thorough exploration of the DNN's functionality and emphasized the importance of hyperparameter optimization in advancing deep learning (DL) technologies. At the outset of our research, we predicted the transmission spectra for both output ports 1 and 2 based on specific input design parameters, including C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 settings at 46 nm and C_4 and C_5 at 18 nm. Subsequently, we compared the actual spectra with the values predicted by

the NN for evaluating both ports, as illustrated in Fig. S8. The transmission spectra integrity of the FDTD method is represented by a continuous orange line in each segment of Fig. S8, while a dashed blue line marks the DNN's predictions. The analysis of the output port 1 spectra is shown on the left side, while the right side illustrates the output port 2 spectra analysis. Subfigures S6a/b, S6c/d, S6e/f, S6g/h, S6i/j, S6k/l, and S6m/n display the transmission spectra for an ascending series of hidden layers within the network, specifically 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, and 13 hidden layers, in the specified sequence. These illustrations provide a clear visual comparison of the experimentally obtained spectra and those predicted by the DNN for each configuration. By carefully adjusting hyperparameters, such as the number of hidden layers and the number of neurons, the analytical accuracy of the DNN is significantly improved. This iterative refinement process allows the model to fully comprehend and articulate the intricate relationships present within the dataset.

Fig. S8. Evaluative comparison between DL and Empirical spectra. This analysis compares the predictions generated by DL models to the empirical spectra of various architectures. The scenarios analyzed include (a) and (b) 1, (c) and (d) 3, (e) and (f) 5, (g) and (h) 7, (i) and (j) 9, (k) and (l) 11, and (m) and (n) 13 hidden layers with both output port 1 (left panels) and output port 2 (right panels).

The insights provided by this enhanced model are invaluable for understanding the operational dynamics of the system under study. This account demonstrates the critical importance of hyperparameter optimization in DNNs and showcases the chosen parameters' effectiveness in precise transmission spectra prediction. It engages the reader in computational modeling and its implications for nanophotonics.

Supplement Note 7. The strategy for finding a sharper dip in the transmission spectrum

In this section, we explore a new method that aims to enhance the visibility of a transmission spectrum by creating a more pronounced and deeper trough. Our analysis revolves around the second-order derivative of the transmission spectrum, which is expressed as $d^2x/d\lambda^2$. As shown in Fig. S9, an increase in the peak of the second derivative graph (Fig. S9a) corresponds to a sharper dip in the transmission spectrum (Fig. S9b). This correlation helps us better understand the spectral properties, which is crucial for improving nanophotonic designs. To ensure accuracy and consistency, we obtained the transmission spectra of four structures using the FDTD approach, thereby minimizing any potential discrepancies that DL algorithms may introduce.

Fig. S9. The relationship between dips in the spectrum and its second derivative. An elucidation of the correlation between significant dips in the transmission spectrum and its second derivative. (a) depicts the transmission spectrum, while (b) showcases its corresponding second-order derivative. Notably, a distinct peak in the second derivative plot indicates a more precisely defined dip in the transmission spectrum.

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